

MACHINE LEARNING BASED OPTIMIZED CRICKET TEAM PREDICTION FOR PLAYERS

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Abstract

The selection of the best players by quantifying players' performances is vital for making informed decisions for each series of games. The manual methods of player selection have chances of various issues, which incorporate personal favoritism & disrelish political and social pressure between selectors and players, leading to deficient results. Moreover, its often seen that Pakistan Cricket Team selectors have tried various players for multiple formats and they don't have an appropriate method that identifies this player is best suitable for this particular format of the game. To solve the above-mentioned issues, we propose a novel method, called Machine Learning-Based Optimized Cricket Team Prediction for Pakistani Players (MLOCTP). MLOCTP recommends a squad of 16 players with their specialized roles and a method of player replacement considering essential factors. The detailed analysis demonstrates the excellent performance of MLOCTP in terms of player selection as it provides promising insights for players' future performances. The comparison exhibits that MLOCTP can designate better performers from multiple players as compared to the actual competing players for the ODI team and thus will assure improved team selection for anticipated matches.

Keywords:

Machine Learning, Linear Regression, Prediction, Cricket, Cricket Team selection, Formats of cricket

1. Introduction

Cricket is a popular outdoor game played in various formats at the international level entailing Test matches, One Day International (ODI), and Twenty 20 International (T20I). Besides all three formats, numerous countries have their domestic leagues Pakistan super league (PSL), is the most renowned league to represent Cricket. (Deep Prakash & Verma, 2022; Mahmood et al., 2021) All-rounders have the capability of both disciplines either best in bowling or batting. A team is usually a combination of batsmen, bowlers, and all-rounders. (Manage et al., 2020). A bowler can bowl a maximum of 10 overs in an ODI match. A batsman can score one-two or a maximum of 6 runs on a single ball and a bowler can bowl 6 balls in an over. A batsman can be dismissed in multiple ways to conclude his inning such as stump out, catch out, run out, etc (J Knight, 2023).

ODI is a type of limited overs cricket played between two teams at the international level. Each team bats only once in ODIs, and plays 50 overs with 10 wickets in hand., each side's innings finishes either their 10 wickets fall or their allotted number of overs has been accomplished (Farooq et al., 2021) International Cricket Council (ICC) is the prime governing body of cricket, with the authority to orchestrate all cricket events worldwide (Mondal et al., 2023). Pakistan Cricket Board (PCB) is the major governing authority of cricket in Pakistan. PCB supervises and assembles all matches and tours of Pakistan's national cricket team such as the T20Asia cups, world cups, etc (Khan et al., 2023).

Before any cricket series selectors declare a set of players for the national team squad each player's performance varies depending on multiple factors such as the player's recent performance, the opposition he is performing against, and the ground on which the match is being played, etc (Robel et al., 2024) The existing method of cricket player selection is based on selectors and coaches. The human selection mechanism is grounded on perception & biasness which declines its efficiency. (Vetukuri et al., 2021). Existing methods of player selection consider the performances of the single format of the game for team selection for ODI. However, in actual team selection players are not selected considering their performances in only one format of the game. (Md. Robel et al., 2023). A host country is a country in which the matches have been played between two teams, various countries have a diverse impact on the performances of players some players tend to perform well in some countries and some or not so it's essential to explore this factor (Qadeer, 2021).

No such method of player selection is available that uses the data of various formats for the team selection of one format for the ODI for any country by considering the host country. To address the above-mentioned issues, this paper proposes an algorithm called, machine learning-based optimized cricket team prediction for Pakistani players (MLOCTP). The proposed algorithm is comprised of three segments. The first one is to find out players' roles such as top-order batsmen, middle-order batsmen, tail-enders, and bowlers (spin & fast), etc. by extracting information from data. The second is to find out ratings by giving weightages to the basic performance measures of the players such as runs, batting average (BA), strike rate (SR) for batsmen and overs, bowling average (BA), and economy rate (ER) for bowlers for each format separately. The third one is to find out optimal players from multiple formats for ODI by assigning weightages to rating values and enact ranking for lineup optimization.

In addition, the main contribution of the proposed work is summarized below:

- **Multiple Format's Data:** The main idea behind using data from various formats is if the player is performing well in one format it might indicate his suitability in another format. MLOCTP provides a mechanism for ODI's player selection by incorporating the data of different cricket formats because when athletes are selected, they are not only selected for playing in one format.
- **Player's Evaluation Based on Weightages:** MLOCTP assign weightages to performance measure for players' evaluation for each format and through assigning weightages to rating points provides a mechanism of merged ranking that classifies players by their roles such as best batsmen, bowlers, all-rounders, and wicket keepers for ODI.
- **Line up Optimization:** lineup is how many batsmen, bowlers (fast& spinners), and all-rounders will be included in the team for a specific host country MLOCTP provides a method of lineup optimization for Pakistani players Moreover, gives a method of player replacement if some of the players are not performing well.

Related Work:

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Related work is elaborated in the next section. Section III describes a complete overview of MLOCTP and all the steps involved. Section IV describes the performance evaluation outcomes while Section V offers the conclusions. The after-mentioned literature covered some aspects that are associated with team selection. Cricket is a game played among two teams of 22 athletes. Test, ODI, and T20I are three internationally familiar formats of cricket. ODI is a limited over format played between 2 teams having international status with 50 overs. The Cricket world cup is conducted after every four years in ODI(Chaturangi et al., 2025). The manual team selection method has numerous demerits. Such as personal liking/ disliking between players and selectors, biases towards specific athletes, social & political pressure, etc.(Jadhav et al., 2021; Weerakoon & Halloluwa, 2024).

To make that particular procedure easy an adaptive neuro-fuzzy-based model has been developed which takes into account various factors of players. It's hard for the selection committee to predict the performance of players based on prior records (Siripurapu et al., 2017). A manual analysis of all previous stats of every player is almost impossible. Another work has found on team selection researcher not only consider players' performance based on cricket data but also considered weather-related data set for better prediction of players using a random forest classifier (Kapadia et al., 2022) The selection of an optimal squad with multiple expertise is problematic in T20I. So by considering the requirements of cricket a new method named "Binary Integer Programming has been introduced for the selection of an optimal squad. (Bhattacharjee & Saikia, 2015; Yin et al., 2023).

2.1. Significance of Player's Performance in Multiple Formats of Cricket

With concern to batting performance, two batting performance measures have been widely discussed in the literature. The first one is batting average (BAT) illustrates the runs scoring ability of players.(Lemmer, 2004) Furthermore, for bowlers three factors are widely explained at first bowling average (BBA) is defined as the total no of runs conceded by the bowler divided by no of wickets obtained. the second one is economy rate can be calculated as the total no of runs conceded by the bowler divided by the of over. (Lemmer, 2006, 2013) Another method of the world's best test cricket team selection by using the TOPSIS method modeled. furthermore, the method used runs, highest scores (HS), BAT, SR,50,100s, innings, etc.

for batting and bowlers (BBA), ER, SR, wickets, etc. (Chakraborty et al., 2018)

In addition, by utilizing machine learning researchers have found the best batsman and bowlers by considering some basic performance indices such as hard hitter, finisher, consistent, economy rate, wicket-taker, etc. for T20I. (Prakash et al., 2016). The researchers have discussed a method based on principal component analysis by using some basic factors such as BAT, Runs, SR, 4s, 6s, BBA, wickets, etc for T20I. (Manage & Scariano, 2013) Other studies found on batting order and optimal lineup selection for ODI by using principal component analysis using various features for batting and bowling such as BAT, BBA, SR, innings, milestones Boundaries, ER, Wickets, Milestones, etc. (Shanto & Awan, 2019).

2.2. Player's Performance Prediction Applying Machine learning in Cricket

The deep performance index (DPI) is a novel index formed by using machine learning which reflects the performance of players (batsmen and bowlers) for team ranking in T20I. After finding limitations in MVPI (Most Valuable Player Index) which only ranks the players who have been playing for a long time. (Bajwa et al., 2025; Prakash et al., 2016) A logistic regression-based CART method has been proposed used to examine home field benefits based on the opposition's geographic location. The home field considers more beneficial for multiple teams whereas south Africa has more chances in 72% of that feature (Jayalath, 2018).

Researchers used various machine learning classifiers for effective prediction, but Random Forest was found more effective for both problems. (Ali et al., 2025; Passi & Pandey, 2018) The proposed work has an accuracy of 91% by suggesting relative team strength against other teams formed a unique feature for prediction. However, researchers have done fruitful work but some factors are not incorporated (Agarwal et al., 2017).

2.3. Impact of Host Country on Players

Some players tend to perform well in some countries and some or not so it's essential to explore the performances of multiple players in various countries. South Africa and England, New Zealand have fast and bouncy pitches that are better for limited-over matches. Moreover. Slow and dusty pitches are found in Asian countries; support spinners flat pitches exist in the subcontinent usually helpful for batsmen furthermore also supportive for fast bowlers. (Passi & Pandey, 2018). Some players can perform well in some countries and some do not as represent by their stats. That particular attribute contributes well to the general nature of pitches for playing the performance of players. Various host countries have different pitches, and various players perform differently on different pitches. (Gupta, 2004).

MLOCTP Depiction for Weightage Allocation and Line-Up Optimization:

Figure 1 indicates the flow of MLOCTP. MLOCTP entails data for three purposes: the first one is to evaluate players' performances from their stats. The second one is to identify players by their roles furthermore delineate which players have the best performances in a match the third one is to recognize the winning combinations of multiple international teams which have already been played in various host countries.

Ball-by-ball data as cited in Figure 1 assists to analyze the statistics of players such as how a batsman played against fast and spin bowling and his level of scoring runs collectively in matches. Inning-by-inning data is supportive for exploring the players' performance considering the others playing eleven and identifying the various winning international teams.

On the other hand, from ball-by-ball data batting averages, strike rates, the whole team batting averages, and whole team strike rates, furthermore from inning-by-inning data bowling averages, economy rates, whole team bowling averages, and whole team economy rates were extracted. Moreover, from these features, a player ranking mechanism has been anticipated separately for each format. In addition, two ratings were derived for each batsman so data aggregation has performed for both for a single numeric rating. Weightages are allocated to the various ratings of multiple player's ratings in multiple formats for single aggregated final ratings. From sorting the ultimate ratings final ranking of players derives which leads to squad selection. From squad selection, the pre-tournament team was selected. Linear regression can predict the expected performance of the players. Moreover, Linear regression is employed on players of the squad for player replacement in tournament team selection.

Figure-1: Architecture of MLOCTP Method

The after-mentioned data sets from domestic and international formats of cricket are utilized for the present research:

- i. Ball-by-ball data of 215 players from 19-Jan-2019 to 27-Dec-2019 of 151 matches.
- ii. Inning by-inning data of 374 players from 19-Jan-2019 to 27-Dec-2019 of 151 matches.
- iii. Inning-by-inning data of 42 ODI matches played in 2019.

Dataset (i) was taken from <https://www.espnricinfo.com/> and <https://www.pcb.com.pk/> whereas dataset(ii)&(iii) was extracted from <https://www.espnricinfo.com> only.

3.1. Performance-Based Batsmen's Ranking and Ranking Index

The weightage distribution method of each player specifies how greatly the player will contribute to his team in the form of a percentage. Player weightage allocation is a technique to ascertain the prominence of a player for his team. Dataset(i) is the source of the following experiment and it helps to calculate the player's previous performances on the bases of which the ranking mechanism has developed.

For ranking a batsman, considered features for players are player runs scored (PRS), player batting average (PBA), Player strike rate (PSR), whole team batting average (WTBA), and whole team strike rate (WTSR). The batsman rating (BTR) and the ranking index were obtained from the Eq. (1).

$$BTR \left[\left((50 * (PBA/WTBA * PRS)) \right) + \left((50 * (PSR/WTSR * PRS)) \right) \right] = \quad (1)$$

Eq. (1) enumerate batsmen rating points by dividing the player's batting average by all players' aggregated batting average and multiplying the figure with player-run scored furthermore multiplying the whole figure with 50 weightages. Furthermore, the player strike rate is divided by all players' aggregated strike rate and multiplied by the player's runs scored proceeding with multiplying the whole figure with 50 weightages, Moreover, after adding both the opening and closing parts of the equation acquiring a single numerical value which are the ranking points of batsmen.

All ranking points are sorted in descending order for acquiring the required list of top batsmen who are best for one format with a ranking index. Moreover, ranking index 1 depicts the top batsman. The two rating points for the same batsman against fast and spin bowler are calculated individually from the above equation using the data set (i)&(ii).

After computing the rating points separately, the rating points are merged such as the rating points of one batsman against fast bowlers and the rating points of a similar batsman against spin bowler are added to get the single rating points of the specific batsman to explore which batsman is most preferable against both types of bowlers. Divergent weightages are given to different formats for players' evaluation.

3.2. Performance-Based Bowler's Ranking and Ranking Index

For ranking of bowler, the requisite is to formulate a generic equation so considered features for players are overs, bowlers' bowling average (BBA), bowler economy rate (BER), whole team bowlers bowling average (WTBBA), and whole team economy rate (WTER). The dataset (ii) is the source after the mentioned experiment. The bowler rating (BWR) is obtained from the Eq. (2)

$$BWR = \left[\left((50 * BBA/WTBBA) \right) + \left((50 * BER/WTER) \right) \right] / OVERS \quad (2)$$

Eq. (2) computes bowler ranking points by dividing the bowler bowling average by all player's aggregated bowling averages and multiplying the figure by 50 weightages. Moreover, in the second end divide the bowler economy rate with all players' aggregated economy rate by multiplying the figure by 50 weightages. Furthermore, after adding both the opening and closing parts and dividing the whole figure with total overs bowled by the bowlers in the whole competition to acquire a single numerical value which is the ranking points of bowlers. All ranking points are sorted in ascending order for a required list of top bowlers which are best for one format with a ranking index. Moreover, the lower-ranking index depicts the top bowler, and ranking index 2 shows some points higher than the top bowler and so on.

3.3. Ranking of All-Rounder and Ranking Index

All-rounder is a player having a specialty in both batting and bowling. Having precise all-rounders is crucial for the right combination of players. For ranking of all-rounder batting and bowling, both statistics are utilized. All-rounder ranking is obtained from the Eq.(3).

$$ALR = [RIB + RIBW] \quad (3)$$

Eq. (3) indicates the method for extracting the ranking index of all-rounders, after analyzing both the

batsman and bowler's ranking indexes separately aggregation is applied to both ranking indexes as from the batting dataset if an all-rounder has a ranking index of 5 and from the bowling dataset same all-rounder has a ranking index of 6 so add both ranking indexes. Furthermore, after encapsulation the ranking index is sorted in ascending order, the lower value from the all-rounder denotes the top all-rounder from the rest of all.

3.4. Multi-format Batsman and Bowlers Ranking (MFBR) along with Merged Ranking Index

MLOCTP is the method of ODI team selection considering the performances of all formats of players. MLOCTP method not only ruminates the ODI players but also tests T20 players for ODI team selection.

Ratings of players are attained from Eqs.(1) and (2) moreover, the list of top batsmen, bowlers, and all-rounders is extracted from all formats. For analyzing which specific player is best suitable for ODI requisite are aggregated rating points of every format 's ratings of each player. For merging ranking points of each format into a single ranking point, the whole process is described.

A merged ranking index is essential to acquire a single value for analyzing and exploring which batsman has higher ranking points among all remaining that provides single merged ranking points of all formats of each player. The multi-format ranking index of each player can be obtained from the following Eq. (4).

$$\text{MFBR}=[(25*\text{ODI})+(20*\text{LISTA})+(10*\text{PSL})+(10*\text{T20DOM})+(15*\text{T20IN})+(12*\text{Test})+(8*\text{FC})]$$

(4)

In the above Eq. (4) multi-format batsman ranking indexes are computed from the rating points of each player in a specific format multiplied with distinct weightage values. As players are selected for ODI so higher weightages are allocated to the ranking points of ODI players 25 out of 100. Moreover, 20 to LIST A,10 to Pakistan super league (PSL),10 to T20 domestic(T20D),15 to T20 international,12 to test international, and 8 to First class Cricket (FC) rating points of each player's total of 100.

Furthermore, the extracted single merged rating points of each player are sorted in descending order for the acquisition of the merged ranking index. The higher-ranking index exhibits the superiority of batsmen over others in the list which represent the top batsmen for ODI alongside all players.

For identifying top bowlers, Eq. (4) is used for calculating the rating points of bowlers. Furthermore, the extracted single merged rating points of each player are sorted in ascending order for the acquisition of the merged ranking index. The lower the-ranking index exhibits the superiority of bowlers over other bowlers.

3.5. Line Up Optimization Criteria for Host Country

A squad comprised of some batsmen, bowlers, all-rounders, and wicketkeepers total of 16 players for the ODI. The playing 11 are selected by analyzing the dataset (iii) after the selection of playing 11 the remaining 5 players are selected as a backup for playing 11. In this section, we present criteria for a player's selection for playing in a particular host country. For this section, data sets (ii) and data set (iii) are utilized. From a prediction point of view after analysis of our dataset, it's come to that linear regression will work well with our data.

After ranking the training dataset of each player was passed to linear regression separately. runs were used as the dependent variable while the batting average was the independent variable for batsmen & All-rounders. Furthermore, runs conceded were the dependent variable for the independent variable economy rate. Average wickets were the independent variable for independent variable wickets. since each player has a separate performance in every host country so each player has a separate dataset. If a player is on an international debut, then his record from domestic cricket has been used as his stats.

Pseudocode of Players selection & Replacement using MLOCTP

1. Initialization
2. list ← list of all batsmen in the team
3. btrf ← get features of a batsman from data set(i)
4. For all batsmen b in the list do
5. data ← dataset (i)
6. brns ← runs scored by the batsmen against fast bowler
7. bavg ← batting average of batsmen against fast bowler
8. wtba ← whole team's batting average against fast bowler
9. bsr ← batting strike rate of batsmen against fast bowler
10. wtsr ← whole team's strike rate against fast bowlers
11. End For
12. rbtf ← get rating of batsman against fast bowler from equation 1
13. list1 ← list of top batsmen with ranking index
14. For all batsmen b in the list do
15. data ← dataset(i)
16. brns ← runs of batsmen against spin bowler
17. bavg ← batting average of batsmen against spin bowler
18. wtba ← whole team's batting average against spin bowler
19. bsr ← bating strike rate of batsmen against spin bowler
20. Wtsr ← whole team strike rate against spin bowler
21. End For
21. rbts ← get rating of batsman against spin bowler from equation 1
22. agr ← rbtf + rbts
23. list2 ← list of available batsmen against spin bowling with ranking index
24. bwrf ← get features of bowlers from data set(ii)
25. list ← list of all bowlers available in the team
26. For all bowlers b in the list do
27. data ← data set(ii)
28. bba ← bowler's bowling average
29. wtba ← whole team bowlers bowling average
30. ber ← bowler economy rate
31. wtba ← whole team blowers bowling average
32. ovr ← total overs bowled by the bowler
33. End For
34. alr ← allrounder ranking
36. rib ← ranking index of players from batting dataset

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37. ribw←ranking index of allrounder from bowling dataset
38. Mfbr← multi-format batsman and bowlers ranking for ODI
40. Mfbr←give 25,20,10,10,15,12,8 weightages to various ratings of multiple formats
41. Dsbl← for batsmen sort descending order and get a list of top batsmen
42. Asbl←for bowlers' sort in ascending order and get a list of top bowlers
43. Arl← aggregate ranking index from batting data set and ranking index from bowling dataset
44. Ts←Select team by considering Host country including 5 extra players
45. If Model player=actual player THEN
46. Performance of the player is verified on Ground for Next Match
47. Else If model player ≠ actual player THEN
48. Performance will be predicted by the Model for the next match
49. Else If
50. Predicted player performance > =Real Player THEN
51. Prediction is accurate// No replacement Required
52. Else
53. MLOCTP player performance < =Real player THEN
54. Then replacement made
55. End

```

4. Performance Evaluation:

In this section, we evaluate the performance of the proposed MLOCTP method and compare the results with actual performance of players in cricket matches. Two rating mechanism was used for predicting the performances of players for ODI.

4.1.Evaluation of performance measures of players:

Since the data set comprised on performance of various players in multiple formats. The performance of every player has been evaluated separately in each format based on various features. on the basis of those ratings of multiple players has identified using the Eqs. (1) and (2) After that for analyzing which players are best suitable for ODI the rating points of every category of player has presented in the following section.

4.2.Multi-format Batsman Ranking (MFBR) along with Merged Ranking Index

The multi-format ranking index of each batsman is obtained from Eq. (4) Total 27 batsmen are extracted which are playing in various formats at the international and domestic levels.

Figure-3:MLOCTP top ranked batsmen for ODI in 2021

4.3.Multi-format Bowlers Ranking (MFBR) along with Merged Ranking Index

The multi-format ranking index of each bowler is obtained from Eq. (4) Total 22 bowlers are extracted which are playing in various formats at the international and domestic levels.

Figure-4:MLOCTP Top Ranked Bowlers for ODI in 2021

4.4.Ranking of All-rounder and Ranking Index

The multi-format ranking index of each allrounder is obtained from Eq. (3) Total 15 allrounders are extracted which are playing in various formats at the international and domestic levels. After the merged ratings of bowlers and batsmen, the top 10 allrounders are display in Table 3.

Figure-5: Top 10 all-rounders selected by MLOCTP for ODI

4.5. Team selection for Pakistan as Host Country and Players Replacement

For team selection for Pakistan as a host country, by utilizing the winning combination of all teams which has already played in Pakistan players are selected from dataset(iii). The final comparison shows the actual players and model's selected players.

Figure-6: Comparisons of Batsmen for Pakistan as a Host Country

The above-mentioned Figure 6 displays the comparisons of batsmen of predicted players and actual players in the third match.

Figure-7: Predicted Performance of Bowlers for Pakistan

The above-mentioned Figure 7 displays the performance of predicted bowlers in the third match. The

clustered bar graph is showing the predicted economy rate and wickets of bowlers.

4.6. Team Selection for South Africa as a Host country and Players Replacement

Figure-8: Comparisons of Batsmen for South Africa as Host Country

The above-mentioned Figure 8 displays the comparisons of batsmen of predicted players and actual players in the third match.

Figure-9: Predicted performance of bowlers for South Africa

The above-mentioned Figure 9 displays the performance of predicted bowlers in the third match. The clustered bar graph is showing the predicted economy rate and wickets of bowlers.

4.7. Team selection for England as a Host country and Players Replacement

Figure-10: Comparisons of Batsmen for England Host Country

The above-mentioned Figure 10 displays the comparisons of batsmen of predicted players and actual players in the third match.

Figure-11: Top 10 all-rounders selected by MLOCTP for ODI

The above-mentioned figure 11 displays the performance of predicted bowlers in the third match. The clustered bar graph is showing the predicted economy rate and wickets of bowlers.

Conclusions

Sports analysis provides fruitful insights for exploring novel dimensions of multiple categories of players which assist the team management coaches and selectors considering different perspectives of the game, moreover beneficial in team selection mechanism. The above-mentioned work proposed a novel MLOCTP based algorithm for player selection considering numerous valuable factors by analyzing the data of their several formats. Our MLOCTP method contributes well in presenting desired outcomes by ranking the players taking into account their roles, selecting the one-day international team for Pakistani players.

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